

A

R5P: Ribose-5-Phosphate
 PRPP: 5-phosphoribosyl-pyrophosphate
 E4P: D-Erythrose-4-Phosphate
 PEP: Phosphoenolpyruvate
 DAHP: 3-deoxy-D-arabino_heptulosonic acid 7-phosphate
 AL: 2-Acetolactate
 AHB: 1-aceto-2-hydroxy butyrate
 KIV: 2-ketoisovalerate

B

DXP: 1-deoxy-d-xylulose 5-phosphate
 AIR: 5-aminoimidazole ribotide
 pABA: para-aminobenzoate

